

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: TOMMY****FIRST NAME: ALLIEU****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. What is the research's perspective of what research is?

- A continuous focus on intrinsic benefits enhancing personal understanding that includes more altruistic focus on benefits to the larger community.
- A scientific way of answering or resolving questions through data collection, analysis to get a conclusion and then make achievable.¹**
- Research outcomes are evidence-based, provokes critical thinking and not individual beliefs and sentiment.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. *Ninth Edition* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 22.

- The researcher is aware that the community that reads the research is huge and may share the same interest in supporting, testing and responding to the research content.

2. **Explain the ways to propose a working hypothesis**

- Working hypothesis contains the relevant variables of the specific group being studied and predicted outcome of the experiment/analysis
- Statement or plausible answer, that can be tested by scientific research and tests the relationship between two or more variables worth writing before you start your experiment or data collection.²**
- Involves statistical hypothesis testing, then a null hypothesis will also be written as the default versus the alternative hypothesis.
- A hypothesis thought of in terms of a scientific experiment as a proposed or predicted answer to a question.

3. **What are the three kinds of sources of research literature?**

- Whether or not a source can be considered both primary and secondary, depends on the context .

² Ibid., 30-32.

The significant sources of research literature are primary, secondary, and tertiary with thin boundaries between them.³

Each field has its own peculiar source of research information for dissertation development, clinical trials in the pharmaceutical companies, social change curious groups and other articles.

Researchers can use the indexing and alerting services of the secondary literature to find out what has been published in a field.

4. **How do you construct your research argument?**

Presenting reasons and evidence to a silent audience.

An argument whose goal is to having a conversation with a community of receptive but skeptical colleagues.⁴

Friendly but thoughtful exchange aimed at developing and testing the best case you and them can present together.

The goal is not to devise clever rhetorical strategies to convince your readers to accept your claim but to tests your assertion, and support so that you can make the best argument possible for the readerables.

³ Ibid., 37.

⁴ Ibid., 38.

5. **How is the planning of the first draft of research paper done?**

- It must be interesting to grab the readers' attention, but it must also give a great deal of information so that the subject of the research paper is clear.
- The difficulty is that a research paper is usually argumentative, so opposing opinions might need to be.
- Good introduction might begin with background information, surprising statistics, a controversial question, a relevant quotation, a definition, an opposing opinion in academic research papers avoid using, personal experiences, humorous stories, a list of facts that prove the thesis to be correct.
- Start writing about the part of your topic that you find most interesting instead of to start at the beginning.⁵**

6. **What are the steps taken in the drafting of final research conclusion?**

- The main objective of a conclusion is to provide an answer/resolution to the research question posed in the introduction.

⁵ Ibid., 56-58.

The conclusion's first task is to summarize the arguments that were presented in the body of the paper by focusing on the connections between the main ideas and the thesis.⁶

A conclusion makes clear how the paper makes a valuable contribution to a field of research.

The conclusion is an account of the research dissertation body and focuses on the outcomes of the argumentation.

7. What are the four documents developed to complete dissertation research writing process?

Research is an original work that search for an answer to question(s) with a studious inquiry aimed at discovering facts.

Some people only write the dissertation prospectus and the dissertation and ignore other documents that improve the quality of the research.

The dissertation concept note is what is usually reviewed for approval by the committee, while the dissertation manuscript helps meet the requirement of a social scientist to disseminate research

⁶ Ibid., 110-111.

- To conduct dissertation research the student should consider the following four documents, dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation and dissertation manuscript.⁷**

8. **What is plagiarism?**

- Plagiarism is a breach of academic integrity.
- It is a principle of intellectual honesty that all members of the academic community should acknowledge originators of the ideas.
- Plagiarism is an academic denial to acknowledge the author for the work.⁸**
- Plagiarism is unethical and can have serious consequences for your future career; it also undermines the standards of your institution and of the degrees it issues.

9. **What are the types of research designs?**

- A good research design serves as the blueprint for how the researcher to collect and analyse data.

⁷ James P. Jr. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research. Second Edition* (Tallahassee, FL: College of Education Florida State University Publications , 2017), 12.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1. Fourth Edition* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

- Research design is the framework of research methods and techniques chosen by a researcher to conduct a study.
- The design allows researchers to sharpen the research methods suitable for the subject matter and set up their studies for success.
- Research design refers to the overall plan, structure or strategy that guides a research project, from its conception to the final data analysis.⁹**

10. **How was the European union founded and grew over time?**

- The European Union started with only six countries.
- European Union was founded in the aftermath of World War II and has grown into a powerful economies in the world. ¹⁰**
- United States of Europe was a part of a humanistic and peaceful dream
- European leaders and thinkers agreed that the only way to sustain peace is to unite countries in economic as well as political terms.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg & Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End. Fourth Edition* (Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications, Inc, 2008), 448.

¹⁰ European Union, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission. Eighth edition* (Bruxelles, BE: Directorate-General for Communication , 2021), 71.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.